

Gender Discrimination in Nayantara Sahgal's *Storm* in Chandigarh

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Abstract

Literature has consistently served as a valuable tool for examining gender relations, sexual differences, and many themes related to women's search for identity in a patriarchal societal structure. Nayantara Sahgal's anecdotal adventure demonstrates her deep concern for the precarious state of women in the narrow-minded culture. Her third novel is titled *Storm in Chandigarh*. It focuses on fostering complex human relationships based on liberty, sincerity, affection, camaraderie, and equality. The novel also expresses a contemptuous objection to the denial of freedom and individuality to women.

Sahgal's concept of a liberated individual transcends the constraints of financial or social independence and transforms into a cognitive or passionate approach. During the storm in Chandigarh, there is a must to redefine ethics and prudence. The protagonist of the novel exemplifies the notion that women possess the advantage of personal autonomy, enabling them to live according to their desires. Therefore, the protagonist converses with the emancipated female character in the story. Saroj, the hero represents the new woman who is striving to maintain her individuality and assert her independence in the challenging environment of emotionally and mentally unfulfilling partnerships. Sahgal aims to address the intense response of women over how they perceive their limitations and themselves. She acknowledges the need for women to strive to understand and define themselves as individuals, rather than solely defining themselves about men. She examines the prolonged suffering of women caused by the forces of discrimination. Sahgal has attempted to portray these pressures in the story. She does not hold men responsible for the unfortunate circumstances of women. Instead, she blames the framework itself. She provided a lucid description of the profound influence of gender discrimination on women's autonomy in the novel.

Keywords: Emancipation, identity, discrimination, women suffering, social independence, culture, etc.

Introduction

The patriarchal structure has been an integral part of Indian society. Historically, women have consistently had a less significant position. When a woman resides in a patriarchal culture, she encounters countless challenges and humiliations. The absence of a husband in a woman's life is deemed a deplorable condition in our society, resulting in her being regarded as insignificant. Society condemns individuals who defy its laws, labelling them as societal transgressors. In a patriarchal society, women's role is scrutinised and evaluated more closely, especially when they fail to meet the expectations set by men.

In India, there has been a long-standing issue of gender discrimination against women, which significantly impacts their lives. Although India has granted women equal rights, the male-dominated culture still practices gender segregation.

Women have limited access to resources such as education and employment services. Providing equal opportunities to women is crucial, considering them as the future of India. Women are often undervalued and under-compensated for their job. This has hindered women from achieving anything in their lives. Women have a crucial role in the process of procreation. Sex is a crucial aspect of human reproduction, involving both males and females, to conceive a child. The patriarchal structure of Indian society, which perpetuates the oppression of women, has contributed to the persistent preference for male children in India.

The practice of aborting female children is a cruel and uncivilised phenomenon that is prevalent in Indian society, and it highlights the inferior position of women in the country. Indian women generally do not achieve education. Although literacy rates are increasing, female education is deemed less significant. The oppression of women has resulted in the establishment of unequal pay for women, with Indian women earning on average 64% of what their male counterparts get for the same job and level of qualification.

Gender discrimination against women is initiated by men due to their lack of self-control and leadership. Although women are granted equal rights, this may not be widely acknowledged by others. In practical terms, men have a weak understanding and adherence to

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land and property rights. Women are denied the social right to assert ownership over property. Without using their names, they do not possess any legal entitlement to inherit a share of their parent's property.

The patriarchal system diminishes the status of women to a subordinate position and maintains its structure through myths and traditions, which unfortunately have become ingrained in society. Indian women's activists and women's activist authors have actively opposed gender segregation and feminist issues inside the Indian patriarchal system, such as discriminatory laws and the practice of Sati. Despite the opposition expressed by several Indian women's activist writers over the male-dominated culture, women residing in present-day India indeed encounter various forms of discrimination.

The patriarchal system in India has influenced the acquisition of land ownership rights and the implementation of gender segregation on female labourers. In recent years, there has been a growing trend of female infanticide and abortion. Indian women's activists perceive them as inequitable. The concept of women being subordinate to men and viewed as the sexual property of men is deeply ingrained in the traditional Indian culture. The spouse believes that he has the entitlement to view her as his puppet and possession. Nayantara Sahgal strongly challenges the mindset that relegates women to a secondary role. The author's acknowledgement of the feminist awareness in her novels reveals her feminist ideology, as noted by Neena Arora in her book, "I have come to this realisation relatively late, despite always having a strong sense of independence" (Nayantara and Doris Lessing 115).

Sahgal's views on gender discrimination are illustrated through the portrayal of her female characters. She desires to unite marriage and prestige. She harbours personal aspirations of matrimony, envisioning a delightful union founded upon matrimonial agreements and mutual trust. Women are individuals, and Sahgal often emphasises this fact in her writings.

Germaine Greer defines the concept of a heterosexual partnership and refers to women as "uncompensated labourers bound by societal expectations" (The Female Eunuch 329). In a patriarchal society, the husband feels a sense of superiority and devalues his partner. A woman's fundamental purpose upon entering the world is to find her rightful place beside a man. Before

marriage, a woman is considered the possession of her father and brother. However, after marriage, the husband gains the authority to exert his will over his wife.

Nayantara Sahgal strongly opposes gender inequality. She would never understand the patriarchal system that devalues women and treats them as objects rather than individuals. In the novel "Storm in Chandigarh," Inder is portrayed as a typical male character who perceives his wife as subordinate and subservient. He exhibits distinct and robust characteristics of masculinity and behaves with a dominant male self-perception. Although he is a father of two children and is about to have another child, he holds the belief that child-rearing is primarily the responsibility of women.

In the novel *Storm in Chandigarh*, Saroj is unable to find a fair and equitable role in her marriage. Inder, her spouse, not only comes from a different cultural background, but he is also a distinct individual in every aspect. Saroj has been brought up in an environment of freedom and has developed a mindset that expects fairness. Regardless, Inder's harsh reaction to a problem she had before her marriage is borne by her. She imparts knowledge to him about it with complete innocence, yet this triggers a troubling suspicion in him. He considers that to be a truly commendable mistake. Inder acknowledges that he has transgressed.

He was infuriated by the order that clearly defined the roles of men and women unless that respected order was violated, disregarded, and ridiculed." Upon experiencing that, he gazed at Saroj with a deep disgust that originated from primal, ancestral masculine instincts (36).

When she married Inder, she had prior experience with early relationships. Society, which adheres to dual ethical principles, finds itself in an alternative situation. However, Saroj is generally not culpable. She is sincere and fully committed to her marriage, but her spouse is concerned about her involvement in this matter. To achieve this, he employs tactics that aim to undermine her self-esteem and completely shatter her sense of innocence. Inder's temperament is enigmatic when it comes to maintaining his ruthless behaviour about the rest of his persona. He is incapable of handling enthusiastic additions or delicacy; his entire disposition is ruthless and assertive.

Saroj desires to break through Inder's rigidity, but Inder continues to bring up past issues and isolates himself, leaving Saroj feeling excluded and unhappy. She feels trapped and frustrated like a bird futilely flapping against a windowpane. (97).

The spouses in Sehgal's *Storm in Chandigarh* reside together under the same roof, although they are emotionally separated by sadness and emptiness. Sehgal acknowledges that sexual pleasure does not always result in emotional and profound harmony. The protagonists in her work have a marriage that is described by sociologists as an "empty shell marriage," which refers to a situation where the partners live together and are legally married, but their marriage lacks any substantial meaning or connection.

Saroj and Inder bear a resemblance to two distinct islands adrift in the same expanse of water, yet they are unable to come together. Inder possesses an atypical bond with Saroj, allowing him to remain detached and indifferent even during intimate moments. Saroj and Rashmi tend to share everything, but Inder believes that sharing a bed is sufficient for anyone's requirements. Saroj desires to share all of her experiences with him. She is enthusiastic about labour. Inder needs only one link with her that is contingent upon the existing harmony. He may be her romantic companion, but not her spouse.

Engaging in a leisurely walk under the moonlight was considered to be a frivolous use of time. That type of backup has repeatedly posed a challenge for him, just like going for a walk with her became a futile waste of time, as he was seized by an impatience to return to his work. Inder Saroj is confused. She is required to disclose all information, only whenever she attempts to speak, Inder forcefully suppresses her and responds harshly in a manner that confuses her about which topics to discuss with him and which ones to avoid. Inder's presence brings to her attention all of her shortcomings, causing her to feel both exceptional and anxious.

Saroj effectively interacts with Vishal, engaging in balanced conversations with him. She is not attracted to Vishal solely for sexual gratification; she desires to satisfy her soul, to engage in unrestricted and sincere conversation like Saroj and nothing more. Vishal and Saroj are collectively their individuals.

This fellowship revitalises her vigour. She informs him,

I was contemplating that true relaxation can only be achieved in the presence of someone who does not evoke fear (91).

Vishal too experiences a sense of collective identity and contemplates it.

Inder lacks the need for companionship. He seeks it extramaritally. He finds Mara to be more friendly and expresses his sincere attention towards her. Saroj is drawn towards Vishal because of her depression. The male's self-perception and sense of superiority hinder the achievement of total harmony among peers. According to Jasbir Jain, Inder has something within him that excludes her and is unaffected by her feelings (Sahgal 45).

Indubitably, even simple pleasures such as deriving enjoyment from the rain are unattainable with Inder, yet they come effortlessly to Vishal. There exists a perfect alignment of intellects, and Vishal is the ideal companion in the truest sense of the term. The recognition of this inherent similarity and understanding is mutual.

Another couple, Jit and Mara, is seeking to engage in sharing and association. Mara is a strong, Westernised, independent woman who is not approved of. She exudes vitality and intellect but remains distant and detached. The narrative of Jit and Mara is highly exceptional. Jit's organiser is devoid of any skeletons. He possesses qualities of warmth, empathy, and compassion; nonetheless, Mara does not experience a sense of fulfilment. She requires someone to exercise control and power over her. Jit's lack of action is severely affecting her, causing her to lose vitality. Inder is a source of vitality in her daily life, making her feel rejuvenated. She is a woman who does not have any children; Jit's resignation has caused her life to become monotonous and without variety. Inder's substantial presence revitalises her and she finds it preferable. Despite Inder's occasional indifference towards her, she still loves him. It seems that Jit lacked something, and Inder fills that void.

With Jit as her spouse and Inder as her companion, her life reaches a state of fulfilment. Perhaps Mara's fear stems from her outgrowing Jit. Her marriage to Jit was a hasty decision made solely to seek solace and make amends.

Jit possesses a sensitive and amiable disposition, although he fails to make a significant impact, unlike Inder. She requires Jit to exhibit more human characteristics, including all the inherent flaws and limitations of being human. The fact that Jit succumbs to all of her desires,

shows no concern for anything, and even when injured, does not display signs of anger are the realities that Mara detests. She vigorously shakes Jit to rouse him from sleep. In contrast to Jit's lack of action, Inder's audacity is appreciated.

She seems angry with Jit's sophisticated manners, and she finds Inder's dishonourable and merciless behaviour intriguing. She is currently perplexed by Inder. Jit also recognises that there is a problem in their connection and makes an effort to get closer to her. During the Christmas night, Mara experiences a sudden and surprising moment of clarity and decides to embark on a new life with Jit. She is deeply moved by the strength conveyed in his words, a type of strength she never anticipated needing as she confidently pursued her life on her own. There is a storm in Chandigarh with a wind speed of 235 kilometres per hour.

In all honesty, Saroj's initial connection only reflects the divergence in their perspectives. She must be recognised as an autonomous individual and must acknowledge a partnership based on equality, rather than viewing her spouse as a possession. Historically, women have been used as mannequins. They have been disregarding it because it is unnecessary to be employed. Marriage has now become a meaningless term in her novels.

Inder is experiencing a sense of illness due to her incapacity to experience enthusiastic satisfaction. He is unable to understand why she is unable to conceive a child, as other women have. From his perspective, a spouse was a component of a commitment aimed at managing her husband's household, children, and career growth. Inder is unable to perceive any other form of relationship with Saroj or, for that matter, even with Nara. Being only surrounded by women unequivocally limits his options. Inder acknowledges that even after a millennium, women will still require the assistance of a professional.

Inder regards Saroj merely as a possession, rather than as a distinct individual. There is unquestionably a familial connection between them.

Inder unequivocally adores Saroj, but only under the condition that she assumes the role of his subordinate or possession. They have lived together and raised children, yet there is no happiness in their relationship. To find fulfilment in her daily life, she requires a compassionate and understanding partner, but Inder is unable to empathise. Later on, the connection between Inder and Saroj revealed the harsh reality of a patriarchal society, where

women live in unfavourable conditions and endure suffering and harassment due to strict social constraints. They are unable to escape from society and consequently accept these circumstances as their inevitable fate.

It can be inferred that in the novel *Storm in Chandigarh*, Sahgal reveals the importance of freedom for personal growth and emphasises the value of individuality, free from societal hypocrisy and pretence. She thoroughly examined the repercussions of gender discrimination on women's autonomy in the novel.

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